

Subgroup Orbit Obstructions in Exponential Diophantine Equations

Ender UYGUN - 10.5281/zenodo.19665124

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1 Introduction

We study the Diophantine equation

$$X^2 - Y^2 = a^b$$

over integers $X, Y \in \mathbb{Z}$, under the condition that $a \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$, where $p > 2$ is prime, and $b \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$.

Our goal is to characterize residue classes $k \equiv Y \pmod{p}$ for which no integer solution exists, via a deterministic obstruction arising from subgroup structure and orbit dynamics in \mathbb{F}_p^\times .

2 Factorization and Reduction

Let

$$u = X - Y, \quad v = X + Y.$$

Then

$$uv = a^b \equiv (-1)^b \pmod{p}.$$

Since $a \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$, we have $p \nmid a$, hence $p \nmid u$ and $u \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$.

3 Subgroup Structure

Let

$$a = \prod q_i^{e_i}$$

where q_i are distinct prime numbers.

Definition 1. Define

$$H = \langle q_1 \bmod p, \dots, q_r \bmod p \rangle \subseteq \mathbb{F}_p^\times.$$

Lemma 1. $-1 \in H$.

Proof. Since $a \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$ and a is generated by the q_i , its residue lies in H . Hence $-1 \in H$. \square

Lemma 2. $u \bmod p \in H$.

Proof. Since $u, v \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $uv = a^b$, by unique factorization in \mathbb{Z} , all prime factors of u lie among $\{q_1, \dots, q_r\}$. Thus

$$u = \pm \prod q_i^{f_i}.$$

Reducing modulo p gives $u \equiv \pm \prod q_i^{f_i} \pmod{p}$. Since $-1 \in H$, we conclude $u \in H$. \square

Define the complement:

$$S = \mathbb{F}_p^\times \setminus H.$$

4 Quadratic Reduction

Let $Y \equiv k \pmod{p}$. Then $X \equiv k + u \pmod{p}$, so

$$X^2 - Y^2 \equiv (k + u)^2 - k^2 = u^2 + 2ku \pmod{p}.$$

Thus:

$$u^2 + 2ku + (-1)^{b+1} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}.$$

5 Vieta Structure

Let x be a generic root corresponding to $u \bmod p$ of the quadratic congruence derived above:

$$x^2 + 2kx + (-1)^{b+1} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}.$$

Define:

$$T(x) = \begin{cases} -x^{-1}, & b \text{ even} \\ x^{-1}, & b \text{ odd} \end{cases}$$

Then $T(T(x)) = x$.

6 Orbit Invariance

Lemma 3. $x \in H \iff T(x) \in H$.

Proof. Since H is a subgroup and $-1 \in H$, it is closed under inversion and negation. Hence $x \in H$ implies $T(x) \in H$ and vice versa. \square

Thus orbits do not cross between H and S .

7 Deadlock Definition

Definition 2. A residue class k is called a **deadlock** if both roots of the quadratic lie in S .

Remark 1. If a residue class k is a deadlock, then the equation $X^2 - Y^2 = a^b$ admits no integer solution with $Y \equiv k \pmod{p}$.

Remark 2. If the discriminant $\Delta = 4k^2 - 4(-1)^{b+1}$ is a quadratic non-residue modulo p , then the quadratic has no roots in \mathbb{F}_p . Such residue classes are trivially obstructed. The notion of deadlock captures the non-trivial case where roots exist in \mathbb{F}_p but are excluded by subgroup dynamics.

8 Parametrization and Orbit Quotient

Let

$$\text{Fix}(T) = \{x \in \mathbb{F}_p^\times : T(x) = x\}$$

and define

$$U = \mathbb{F}_p^\times \setminus \text{Fix}(T).$$

Definition 3. Let $K_{\text{allow}} \subseteq \mathbb{F}_p$ denote the set of residue classes k for which the quadratic congruence has two distinct roots (i.e., $x \neq T(x)$).

Define:

$$\phi(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1-x^2}{2x}, & b \text{ even} \\ -\frac{1-x^2}{2x}, & b \text{ odd} \end{cases}$$

Lemma 4. The map ϕ induces a bijection:

$$U/\langle T \rangle \longleftrightarrow K_{\text{allow}}.$$

Each residue class corresponds to exactly one orbit $\{x, T(x)\}$. Moreover, this parametrization precisely covers those k for which the discriminant $\Delta = 4k^2 - 4(-1)^{b+1}$ is a quadratic residue modulo p , i.e., the cases where roots exist in \mathbb{F}_p .

9 Fixed Points

Let F denote the number of fixed points lying in S .

- If b is odd:

$$x^2 \equiv 1 \Rightarrow x = \pm 1.$$

Since $\pm 1 \in H$, no fixed point lies in S , hence $F = 0$.

- If b is even:

$$x^2 \equiv -1.$$

- If $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$: no solutions $\Rightarrow F = 0$
- If $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$: two solutions, and

$$F = \begin{cases} 0, & \sqrt{-1} \in H \\ 2, & \sqrt{-1} \in S \end{cases}$$

10 Orbit Counting

Since each deadlock residue class corresponds to exactly one orbit in S (whether a 2-element orbit or a fixed point), we obtain:

$$D(p, m) = \frac{|S| + F}{2}.$$

Using the index definition $m = [\mathbb{F}_p^\times : H]$, we have

$$|H| = \frac{p-1}{m}, \quad |S| = (p-1) - \frac{p-1}{m} = (p-1) \left(1 - \frac{1}{m}\right),$$

which yields an exact count.

11 Main Theorem

Theorem 1. Let $m = [\mathbb{F}_p^\times : H]$.

Then the number of deadlock residue classes is:

$$D(p, m) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}(p-1) \left(1 - \frac{1}{m}\right), & b \text{ odd} \\ \frac{1}{2}(p-1) \left(1 - \frac{1}{m}\right), & b \text{ even, } p \equiv 3 \pmod{4} \\ \frac{1}{2}(p-1) \left(1 - \frac{1}{m}\right) + \frac{F}{2}, & b \text{ even, } p \equiv 1 \pmod{4} \end{cases}$$

where $F \in \{0, 2\}$.

Dedication

This work is dedicated to the children who were martyred in the Shajarat al-Tayyiba Girls' Primary School in Iran, which was bombed on February 28, 2026 by Israel and its lackey, the United States.